

Environmental Data Initiative (EDI) Sustainability Plan

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Environmental Data Institute, Inc.

A Non-Stock, Not For Profit, 501(c)(3), Corporation

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1. Organization Summary

Environmental Data Institute, Inc. (EDI) is non-stock, not for profit 501(c)(3) corporation with decentralized, remote US operations. It is presently filing for federal 501(c)(3) tax exempt status, which has not yet been formally assigned. It develops and deploys technology and services for the environmental science FAIR data and research community. EDI was incorporated in 2024 and originated from collaborative work between the University of Wisconsin-Madison and the University of New Mexico.

EDI was founded to become a vehicle of long term sustainability for FAIR environmental science and related data and technologies. Its mission is predicated on the conviction that:

- Humanity will face great and long term environmental challenges
- High quality access to historic environmental science data will be essential in humanities formulation of corrective measures to preserve, restore, and maintain our environment
- This access and associated technologies and services will, long term, reduce the net time and cost to achieving a sustainable, healthy global environment for all of humanity

2. Mission

To our target audience:

Preserving, Publishing, and Studying Data From the Natural World for Generations To Come

To a general audience:

We're a nonprofit organization empowering scientists to create and preserve powerful data that benefits our global environment and protects the future of humanity.

The EDI mission is no less than 100 years and global in scope of impact. The mission is simultaneously altruistic (to the benefit of all life on Earth) and self-serving (to the benefit of humanity) in nature. It includes the development and continuous adaptation of technologies and services to enable and drive positive change, enhanced research and decision making, and global scientific transparency for environmental data.

From articles of incorporation:

“The Environmental Data Institute aims to preserve, make freely available to the global scientific community, and study data from the natural world until such a time when historic environmental scientific data are no longer required to create and maintain a healthy relationship with the natural world that enables humanity’s existence. It additionally aims to develop, deploy, adapt, promote, and otherwise utilize high-quality technologies and services to empower those who depend upon this mission. It shall maintain long-term focus on the aims and appropriately divest itself of activities or opportunities that arise over time not directly related to these aims.”

3. Strategy

The guiding principles behind the adopted EDI strategy are:

- EDI must maintain mission focus across a long period of time

- EDI must remain financially stable through varied economic climates
- EDI will generate technologies and services that are simultaneously valuable to its mission and valuable to non-mission activities

The overarching strategy (in a single run-on sentence) of EDI is to build a premium, light house brand of excellence and support without alienating the academic/scientific community by continuing to offer certain free capabilities and leveraging unmet market needs to develop stable revenue streams while building relationships with grantors and philanthropic organizations and spinning off for-profit ventures to capture market opportunities too large or too much of a distraction to the parent nonprofit and its mission.

3.1. Membership

EDI is a 501(c)(3) non-stock corporation, meaning it does not have equity or shares of ownership. It is a Membership organization. As no financial return from the nonprofit directly is legal or appropriate, EDI would like to incentivize team members and organizations that substantially contribute to the success and stability of the organization by enabling their equity participation in the spinoff for profits that are anticipated to originate from its work. To this end EDI will adopt a policy for capitalization table structure such that Members are provided the opportunity to participate in the equity of the new for profit ventures.

EDI intends to have open conversations with early partners and donors about the most ethical, fair, and legal methods to accomplish this.

3.2. Business model

The business model has three planned phases, each focusing on different sources of financial resources. Subsequent sections of this business plan will focus on Phase 1.

3.2.1. Phase 1: Path to Sustainability

This initial phase of the life cycle of EDI is to validate, formulate, and scale market based revenue while sustaining and growing operations through grants and philanthropy. It is planned to take 3 years with a window of probability extending to 5 years. It will be typified by:

- Low volume, diverse revenue streams
- Research grants similar to ones historically obtained by the team
- Growth, mission, and sustainability motivated philanthropy

3.2.2. Phase 2: Market-based Sustainability

This second phase of the life cycle of EDI is to sustainably pursue its mission and opportunistically collaborate and advance its technology and services. It is planned to last an indefinite period until the requirements of Phase 3 are achieved. It will be typified by:

- Operational financial needs met by annually recurring revenue
- Grants and philanthropy being leveraged to pursue R&D and addressing underserved niche markets

- Periodic spin-off of for-profit ventures designed to grow value and conclude with liquidity event
- Initiate and grow an endowment

3.2.3. Phase 3: Independent Sustainability

This final operating phase of the life cycle of EDI is to sustainably pursue its mission, heavily collaborate, provide grants, and advance its technology and services primarily through the annual proceeds from an endowment. It is planned to last until such a time that the Members decide to wind down the operations of the organization. It will be typified by:

- Operational, R&D, and services financial needs met by annual return on endowment
- Issued grants and sponsored collaborations that advance the mission
- Market based revenues from highly productized, scalable offerings and provided at a highly economized pricing architecture to maintain strong engagement with the market
- Periodic licensing of IP to for-profits to grow endowment and spin-off of for-profit ventures designed to further EDI mission

3.3. Revenue model

EDI is in an experimental mode of engaging with the market on a fee-for-service basis. As such several value offering structures will be tested with a preference towards Subscription/SaaS engagements.

3.3.1. Subscription

Subscriptions will generally be structured to teams and larger groups as SaaS tiers that have different levels of service and number of authorized users. Individual user, and data access engagements will have SaaS tiers with no service, all automated or software based usage.

3.3.2. One-time Purchase

Some services, data products, and data access will have one time purchase mechanisms. Most of these will be structured to allow a lower cost customer engagement as a pathway to an eventual subscription.

3.3.3. Grant Commitment

For single investigator and special case customers, an engagement where the customer commits to include EDI as a line itemed vendor in their grants, and pays EDI upon grant award will be considered.

3.3.4. Freemium

As part of FAIR data principles, mandates of federally funded research, and to maintain a supportive relationship with academic scientists, free access to the platform and data, with an appropriate license, will be maintained.

3.4. Marketing and Communications

Similar to revenue model and customer engagement experimentation, the marketing and communications methods of EDI are in an experimental phase. A general strategy of brand awareness, general communications aimed at the scientific community, and targeted communications to higher revenue opportunity customers will be employed.

Environmental Data Initiative is already globally recognized as a repository for sharing and archiving data following FAIR data guidelines. This brand will be strengthened and built upon for the Environmental Data Institute (EDI).

A preference for data driven and scalable methods will be evidenced across experiments aimed at revenue generation customers. More qualitative methods traditional to academic and scientific markets will also be deployed for more brand and thought leadership oriented communications.

3.5. Long Term Sustainability

Section 3.2 above provides the basic features of three phases of development and their relationship to financial sustainability. It also defines the eventual goal of Independent Sustainability, the ultimate financial goal of the organization. Throughout all phases, revenue based engagements with the market will be developed, maintained, and periodically retired or later offered for free. This accomplishes several things:

- Derisks major economic swings
- Validates needs and value in the market
- Maintains and grows influence of the Institute
- Drives change and adoption of new best practices
- Identifies new opportunities for potential for profit spinoffs

4. Market

4.1. FAIR Data

Several meaningful trends are emerging within FAIR (Findable, Accessibly, Interoperable, and Reusable) data. These provide a timely and opportunistic environment for EDI to establish itself and its offerings in the US market.

4.1.1. General Trend

There is a nation-wide trend towards valuing and practicing FAIR data standards. It is being driven by both federal and local agencies and municipalities, as well as the scientific community.

4.1.2. Funder Mandates

The US federal government is increasingly mandated the adherence of its grantees and internal departments to comply with FAIR data principles as part of research data management practices. The NSF and NIH have placed organization-wide mandates to begin migrating to new standards and practices by the beginning of 2025.

4.1.3. Community and Collaboration

Collaborative efforts among universities, research institutions, industry, citizen scientists, and municipalities are growing the awareness and adoption of FAIR data practices.

4.1.4. Training and Education

There is increased focus and demand for training of educators, researchers, and data managers about FAIR principles and practical application.

4.1.5. Integration and Emerging Technologies

There is a widespread sentiment and emerging need for interoperability of metadata, data, and ontological standards, as well as integration with AI/ML resources that are beginning to find more widespread adoption. This overall points to demand for easier to use tools and resources.

4.2. Macro Trends

Several prominent trends are affecting the environmental science community, particularly in the data management sector.

4.2.1. Climate Change Data Demand

There is a growing national and international emphasis on monitoring contaminants in the environment, indicators and effects of climate change, and the status of aquatic environments. These areas of interest necessitate strong data management resources.

4.2.2. Natural Solutions

There is increased pressure for solutions within environmental management, such as flood protection, watershed management, and wastewater treatment, that are based upon natural systems. The development, monitoring, and effective management of such systems require extensive data collection and often public disclosure requirements.

4.2.3. Technical Advancement

The widespread development and deployment of more advanced soft systems, such as AI/ML and blockchain, in all major fields and industries. There is a strong expectation that these technologies will meaningfully, positively impact the area of environmental data sharing and reuse.

4.2.4. Sustainability and ESG Reporting

There is a national movement to improve the Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) reporting for corporations, large organizations (universities) and municipalities. Along with this are rapidly emerging regulatory and reporting requirements. This demands both access to, and the generation of, substantial amounts of environmental data.

4.3. Unmet Needs

The environmental data repository, publishing, sharing, and data set access market faces several meaningful unmet demands.

4.3.1. Interoperability and Standards

There is a lack of uniformity of standards, protocols, formats, and data management processes across repositories, researchers, and organizations. This complicates the

aggregation and reuse of data from multiple sources and results in frustration, uncertainty, time inefficiency, and less comprehensive analyses.

4.3.2. Ease of Use and Access

The repositories, data packages themselves, metadata, and search tools are typified as generally free, but not user-friendly, easily usable or accessible, and expensive in time.

4.3.3. Sustainable Finances

The vast majority of the 3,000+ diverse repositories are not inherently financially sustainable. There are different funding risk scenarios, however none that match the long term mission associated with their usage. This also tends to lead to outdated hardware, software, and infrastructure, and difficulty keeping abreast of technological advances.

4.3.4. Big Data

Data authors are struggling with the emergence of big data collection and analysis capabilities, but few options for sharing, long term storage, and access. Data sizes will likely only increase over time, leading to difficulties in collaboration, data gathering, analysis, and data retention.

4.3.5. Incorporation of Emerging Technologies

Widespread adoption of newer and advanced technologies, particularly AI/ML, is lacking in this space due to both technical and financial barriers, resulting in decreased analysis quality, data set value, security, and end user ease.

4.3.6. Compliance

Regulations around FAIR data, data privacy, security, misuse, etc. are evolving consistently and at times rapidly. Repositories and research organizations alike grapple with staying abreast of and complying in this environment.

4.3.7. Training

Researchers, data managers, regulators, organizational leaders, and team managers alike lack the needed training to effectively use repositories and related tools and workflows that would maximize the benefit to them.

5. Team

5.1. Leadership

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5.2. Staff

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5.2.1. University Collaboration

Scientific

5.2.2. Data Curation

5.2.3. Technology

5.2.4. Marketing and Operations

5.2.5. Advisory and Volunteer

5.3. Org and Team Growth

5.3.1. Internal

Industry-traditional reporting structures will be followed for internal team members. Management and guidance of collaborative contributors, at Universities or otherwise independent from EDI, will be managed by internal team member with subject matter expertise and accountability.

5.3.2. Key Hires

Hires are timed to correlate with business progress milestones and thus can be accelerated or decelerated depending upon rate of progress. It should be noted that the existing academic team will continue to require substantial resources, making the addition of business professionals essential to achieve progress milestones and that scaling back or slowing down team growth may only partially decrease burn rate.

- **Q1:** FT VP/Dir Sales, FT MarComm & Creative Mgr/Dir, PT Technology PI (Dr. Doan)
- **Q2:** PT Web Developer, PT Sales Specialist
- **Q5:** FT Curation Scientist, FT CEO, FT Sales Specialist, PT Full Stack Developer, PT Exec Admin, PT Business Advisor, PT MarComm Associate, PT MarComm Analytics Mgr, PT VP HR, PT Full Stack Developer
- **Q7:** PT COO
- **Q9** FT MarComm Associate, FT MarComm Analytics Mgr, FT Exec Admin

6. Product & Solutions

6.1. Solutions Matrix

Below is a collection of potential sales types and price points. Each has a distinct value set, service and technology level, and cost of delivery. These are the early points of experimentation to identify practical price point, latent demand, price sensitivity, sales cycle, COGS, and other factors that will impact the ability to grow that particular revenue stream.

NOTE: Pricing Hypothesis: **Confidential At Time of Publication**

Platform		Price (low)	Price (high)	Average Price (\$k)	Sales Cycle (months)	Customer
Enterprise	Subscription	\$x	\$x	\$x	14	cities, states, agencies, large corporations
Large Department	Subscription	\$x	\$x	\$x	6	small cities, departments, universities
Small Department	Subscription	\$x	\$x	\$x	4	municipal and university departments, SMBs
LTER	Subscription	\$x	\$x	\$x	3	LTER sites or network
Grant Based	One-off	\$x	\$x	\$x	2	investigators, teams, sites
Investigator	Subscription	\$x	\$x	\$x	2	academic, government
Community	Free	\$x	\$x	\$x	1	academics, researchers

Services							
	Training	One-off	\$x	\$x	\$x	4	gathered groups, small depts : enterprise customers
	Curation	One-off	\$x	\$x	\$x	1	investigator : small department
Data Reuse							
	Data Set Creation	Subscription	\$x	\$x	\$x	2	contractors, researchers
		One-off	\$x	\$x	\$x	2	contractors, researchers
	ML Training Data Set	Subscription	\$x	\$x	\$x	1	researchers, tech companies
		One-off	\$x	\$x	\$x	1	researchers, tech companies
	Download	Subscription	\$x	\$x	\$x	2	contractors, tech companies, foreign orgs
		One-off	\$x	\$x	\$x	1	contractors, tech companies, foreign orgs
		Free	\$x	\$x	\$x	1	contractors, tech companies

The goal is to identify, then focus on and scale several, but not all, offerings that present the right profile of price, margin, demand, and COGS. That resulting focus will persist through the cash flow break even point unless a pivot is deemed necessary.

6.2. Offerings Value & Features

6.2.1. Data Publishing & Access

Enterprise

\$xk+/year ARR; cities, states, large universities, .gov agencies, foreign governments/states

Services: transition guidance, training, workshops, premium curation support, product customization

Products: multi-user accounts management, confidentiality/timed publication, central data/document management, self-service repository, big data capable, unlimited download

Values: meet FAIR data needs; solve problems around persistence of data over time and staff turnover; provide control over confidential and publicly releasable data; provide centralized organization point for data; enable compartmentalization of data access across team and organization; align data practices with long term objectives; training and guidance from industry leaders; minimize related in-house IT/IS expenses; reduce data management staffing related expenses; provide confidence to team management; provide publicly trustworthy brand to point to as service provider; create consistency of practice and policy across an organization; reduce risk of data loss; in-house technology upgrades and modernization not needed; continuous tool kit enhancement over time; tracking and reporting on usage/behavioral patterns is possible.

Departmental: Large

\$x-xk/year ARR; Watershed department at City of Seattle; large teams or departments within municipalities or at research institutions with multiple Principal Investigators and group data management needs, large for profit engineering/consulting companies

Services: transition guidance, training, premium curation support

Products: multi-user accounts management, confidentiality/timed publication, central data/document management, self-service repository, big data capable, unlimited download

Values: (see above Values) + premium and enterprise level solution for operation centers that is far more cost effective than development, maintenance, and upgrades of in-house solution.

Departmental: Small

\$x-xk/year ARR; research teams or sites, small engineering/consulting companies

Services: research integration guidance, training, curation support

Products: multi-user accounts management, confidentiality/timed publication, central data/document management, self-service repository, big data capable, free download limit

Value: (see above Values) + provides cost effective operational framework to organize team behavior and data practices around

Principle Investigator

\$x-xk/year ARR; single Principal Investigators research groups, small scientific teams

Services: research integration guidance, training, curation support

Products: central data/document management, self-service repository, big data for fee, free download limit

Value: (see above Values) + helps integrate data collection practices with data storage and publishing; increases visibility and impact of work

Community

\$free; Principal Investigators

Services:

Products: self-guided training, self-service repository, free download of owned data with limit

Value: enables academic, NPO, and citizen scientists to memorialize and publish data without their own technology infrastructure.

6.2.2. Services

Training

\$xk+/year ARR; cities, states, large universities, .gov agencies, foreign governments/states

Services: transition guidance, training, workshops, premium curation support, product customization

Products: multi-user accounts management, confidentiality/timed publication, central data/document management, self-service repository, big data capable, unlimited download

Values: meet FAIR data needs; solve problems around persistence of data over time and staff turnover; prov

Curation

\$xk+/year ARR; cities, states, large universities, .gov agencies, foreign governments/states

Services: transition guidance, training, workshops, premium curation support, product customization

Products: multi-user accounts management, confidentiality/timed publication, central data/document management, self-service repository, big data capable, unlimited download

Values: meet FAIR data needs; solve problems around persistence of data over time and staff turnover; prov

6.2.3. Data Reuse

Data Set Creation

\$x-xk/data set; Principal Investigators

Services: data gathering, data set harmonization, metadata development

Products: developed data set becomes a resalable product

Problem: When new grants initiate, it takes several months for newly hired postdocs or research scientists to come up to speed on a project and produce such a data set, costing both 2-4 months of time and \$x-xk direct expense on salary.

Value: Reduce time to project initiation; reduce unproductive use of funds on inefficient use of researcher time

*ML Training Data Sets

\$ fee/data set or subscription access; Principal Investigators, software developers

Services:

Products: pre-packaged, harmonized data sets designed for ML training and performance benchmarking

Problem: There is a desire to develop AI/ML models for deployment in environmental scientific fields. No standardized or benchmarked training or guided-learning data sets yet exist. Computer scientists traditionally do not have expertise in environmental science data architecture, complexity, interdependence, etc.

Value: Enable AI/ML model performance benchmarking, comparison, and improvement within environmental science fields. Cost and time effective tools for developers that do not have environmental scientific expertise.

*Data Download

\$fee/data volume or subscription access; User types uncertain

Services: search and discovery assistance

Products: search, test analysis, and visualization tools

Problem: Market behavior demonstrates a significant demand for data within the EDI repository. The technology and systems to identify who the data users are, and thus what their use case and needs are is not yet developed. This is an area of future work that has a high probability of some commercial significance. It is straightforward to hypothesize use cases and value, but are not yet verifiable.

Value: Uncertain

7. Competition

7.1. In-house

A broad range of in-house solutions exist tailored to, and representative of, the size and type of organization using it. While specificity of value offering tends to be high in these cases, either cost of operation and upkeep is high or performance and advancement of technology is low. Examples: **Confidential At Time of Publication**

7.2. Not For Profit Organizations (NPO)

Some repositories have had NPOs formed around them as a means to fund and pursue their initial mission, similar to EDI. Within the US, they continue to be narrow in scientific

focus, have minority market stake brands, and struggle with sustainability as they are dominantly grant and philanthropically supported.

Examples: **Confidential At Time of Publication**

7.3. Government & Political

Some US departments and agencies have in-house repositories and solutions. And a single international Alliance is providing thought leadership and guiding repository practices. These display the traditional hallmarks of government projects and programs where there is a high cost of time and frustration with system usage; narrow focus on scientific sub-discipline; and are very slow to update and adapt to new technologies. Examples: **Confidential At Time of Publication**

8. Financials

8.1. Initial Financial Support

It is estimated that cash flow break even from revenue can be achieved in 3-5 years with support in the \$x-xM range. All plans are structured to achieve cash flow break even in 3 years or less, and the range of time and support needed are to account for natural variance while building a new organization and customer base.

8.2. Current assets

Note that all assets here identified are not presently owned by EDI but rather by UW-M, UNM, or the team members themselves.

8.2.1. IP

Certain elements of the software infrastructure may not be fully open sourced yet. Additional software/web based IP will be generated through the transition to a cloud-based infrastructure

8.2.1.1. Know How

Meaningful expertise, knowledge, and operational experience underpin the ability to deliver the current and future value offerings of EDI

8.2.2. Paying Customer

The City of Seattle Department of Watershed Management is a current customer of the Environmental Data Initiative, having a contract for ~\$xk over 7 years with the primary contract holder being UW-M

8.2.3. Relationships

The team collectively has a well established collection of relationships with users, collaborators, regulatory bodies, LTER Network, repositories, universities, and other players in the scientific repository landscape.

8.2.4. Brand

The Environmental Data Initiative has established a core brand of trust, integrity, and high standards that is strong within those who are exposed to it. The brand has not been widely promoted or disseminated.

8.2.5. Data

The collective body of data is demonstrably of value to the market as evidenced by the relatively high organic rate of access and download.

8.2.6. Technology

A fully functional and stable data repository and associated tools, features, and user management exists. It should be noted that the hardware infrastructure supporting this system is now out of warranty and represents both an asset and a liability.

8.3. Projections

8.3.1. Revenue and Cash Flow Break Even

Preliminary modeling suggests that with resource input of \$x-xM, cash flow break even is possible within 3-5 years. The chart below represents a reasonable and informed series of assumptions, presumptions, and known parameters. And experience suggests that realistically building such revenue bases often take longer than projected.

8.3.2. Revenue Projections

Below are preliminary assumptions, presumptions, variables, and factors affecting both revenue and operational cost projections.

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8.3.3. Operational Expense Projections

Below are presumptions of simplified cost estimating %s to be applied to team base salaries to produce operational requirements.

- Fringe Rate 31%
- Ops + G&A 10%
- Annual Inflation 3.0%
- Commission Rate variable by sale type: see revenue controls dashboard
- COGS variable by sale type: see revenue controls dashboard

9. Spin Offs

Below represent solely concepts to be considered or explored and are to be considered purely hypothetical at this point.

9.1. Corporate Environmental reporting

9.2. University In-house data repository replacement: all use cases, not environmental specific

10. Contacts

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